

Crowd Management During Hajj Pilgrimage in Saudi Arabia Literature Synthesis

Sadeq Kadi ^{1*}, Alias Abdullahi ², Syariah Bachok ³, Hashim Abdullahi ⁴

*Department of Urban and Engineering Research, Umm Al-Qura, University, Makkah Saudi Arabia

^{1,2,3} Department of Urban and Regional Planning, Faculty of Architecture and Environmental Design, International Islamic University (IIUM), Jln Gombak, 53100 Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

⁴Department of Urban and Regional Planning, Federal Polytechnic Mubi, PMB, 35, Adamawa State, Nigeria

Abstract Recent occurrences like as the Mina disaster in Hajj, Saudi Arabia in 2015, the Water Festival in Phnom Penh, Cambodia in 2010, and the Love Parade Music Festival in Duisburg, Germany in 2010 have demonstrated how poor crowd control can swiftly turn a heavenly occasion into a tragedy (Alkhadim et al., 2018; Aros-Vera et al., 2020; Illiyas et al., 2013). The aim of the study is to evaluate crowd with regards to its management within the period of Hajj Pilgrimage in Saudi Arabia with the aid of synthesizing literature. The study therefore synthesized literature on crowding at Hajj pilgrimage, crowd management during the Hajj pilgrimage, crowd management an over view, crowd monitoring techniques, crowd measurement models, density and crowd generation, crowd management principles and strategies, pedestrian crowd management strategies, public participation and awareness on pathways regulations, urban design for pedestrian movement, and urban design principles and strategies. In conclusion, there is very strong needs to have pedestrian movement system model (PMSM) for Hajj Pilgrimage Saudi Arabia with a specific focus on the pathway from Arafah to Muzdalifah at Mecca.

Key words: Crowd, Management, Hajj Pilgrimage, Saudi Arabia, and Synthesis

I. INTRODUCTION

Crowd management at Hajj pilgrimage Saudi Arabia has been receiving scholarly contributions. Recent occurrences like as the Mina disaster in Hajj, Saudi Arabia in 2015, the Water Festival in Phnom Penh, Cambodia in 2010, and the Love Parade Music Festival in Duisburg, Germany in 2010 have demonstrated how poor crowd control can swiftly turn a heavenly occasion into a tragedy [1], [2], [3]. Every year, millions of people gather in specific areas throughout the world for hundreds of events. One of the examples of mass gatherings is the pilgrimage to Hajj in Mecca, Saudi Arabia, when millions of people visit Mecca at the same time to undertake Hajj [1].

Months of preparation precede the event. According to [4] the majority of crowd control work is spent on planning, which typically begins at least six months before the event. Planning time should be sufficient to forecast and create crowd-sourced activities [2]. This process has the potential to become a multiagency and private-public partnership effort including government agencies, event planners and managers, emergency services, and municipal authorities, as well as all private and public parties participating in the event's planning. Identifying and prioritizing possible hazards, as well as scripting "what if" scenarios to establish reaction management methods, are all preliminary processes for event organization [2], [4].

Controlling and monitoring the event are key management duties following the planning phase. All these events have one thing in common which is the gathering of a huge crowd in a small geographical region, where individuals enter via checkpoints, remain for a while, and then depart [5], [6]. The design and operation of checkpoints is a critical component of crowd management since the efficiency and efficacy of the admission procedure is governed by checkpoint technology and capacity.

II. CROWD MANAGEMENT DURING THE HAJJ PILGRIMAGE

The term "crowd" often refers to a temporary assembly of individuals in a specific location for a shared cause, with or without a prior gathering arrangement [6]. A pedestrian crowd is a gathering of people who are walking on foot in a specific area within an urban environment, such as sidewalks, streets, or public spaces [7],[8] . Pedestrian crowds are a common occurrence in cities and urban areas, where individuals traverse the built environment by walking [9]. The term "pedestrian" refers to individuals who travel on foot, whether it be for transportation, leisure, or recreational purposes. Pedestrian crowds consist of individuals or groups who share the same space and move in a similar direction [10],[11]. These crowds can be observed in various settings, including sidewalks, pedestrian zones, shopping districts, parks, and other public areas where people gather and walk.

various types of pedestrian crowds can be identified, including commuter crowds, tourist crowds, event crowds, protest crowds, market crowds, rush hour crowds, and nightlife crowds [12],[13]. The behavior and dynamics of these crowds can significantly vary based on specific contextual factors, cultural influences, local customs, and other variables. Sociologist Herbert Blumer developed a popular typology of crowds based on their purpose and dynamics, which includes casual crowds, conventional crowds, expressive crowds, acting crowds, and protest crowds. Other scholars have developed different typologies, such as Mombousse's system of casual, conventional, expressive, and aggressive crowds, and Berlonghi's classification of crowds as spectator, demonstrator, or escaping, to correlate to the purpose for gathering [12], [14], [15].

Crowding is generally linked with high densities; congestion is usually caused by pedestrian movements and walking activities. Crowd management is always an issue when events with fluctuating attendance occur. Crowd disasters at major events are a significant source of concern for event public safety due to the associated fatal accidents and disruptions. To ensure public safety, it is critical to maintain pedestrian flows. Crowd management is the organization and delivery of services to a crowd, which involves planning, training, and information collection. It also includes evaluating a packed event's infrastructure and service suppliers' capacities [6], [16]. Crowd control, on the other hand, refers to the processes for dealing with circumstances in which a crowd is confronted with an emergency, such as a fire or a stampede. Its functions involve developing models and decision-making procedures essential for effective response [17].

Crowd management study began in the early 1890s, with academics focused on the psychological decision-making processes involved in the formation of crowds. Crowd control or management is an effective strategy since it helps to prevent disorder breakouts and potential unrest [18],[19]. Creating a crowd management strategy involves thinking about the operational planning and procedures that will be employed to enable movement during a crowded event. Crowd management aims to reduce severe crowd concentrations and promote rapid mass movement to avoid potentially hazardous incidents by meticulously planning and executing [4], [20]. Crowd management approaches are collaborative efforts between the crowd management team's multiple actors and the crowd that rely on the processing, dissemination, and interaction

of important data and helpful knowledge, with efficiency being critical for the crowd's security and well-being [4]. Figures 1(a), 1(b), and 1(c) depict different intensity of crowd formation during Hajj pilgrimage at various different locations

Crowd Management an Over View

Assessing a crowd involves considering several factors as shown in figure 3.1. First, the size of the crowd plays a crucial role in understanding its dynamics and potential implications. Larger crowds generally require more attention to crowd management and security measures [10],[7]. Second, the area of occupation provides context for crowd control strategies, as different environments may require specific measures to ensure safety and order [9],[21]. Furthermore, distinguishing between static and moving crowds helps in determining the best approach for crowd management and planning exit routes. Lastly, assessing the direction and purpose of the crowd aids in understanding its intentions and potential impact [22],[23]. Whether the crowd is gathering for a celebration, protest, or other reasons can inform decision-making and response strategies. By considering these factors, organizers and authorities can effectively evaluate and respond to crowds in a comprehensive manner.

Figure 2 Shows Assessing Crowds.

Pedestrian disasters, particularly panic stampedes, pose significant and complex challenges in crowd management [24],[25]. Despite the presence of extensive security forces and crowd control techniques, human stampedes remain a recurring threat during large

events, often resulting in the loss of thousands of lives. In the context of this study, density and crowding are distinct concepts. Density refers to the physical area available to a specific group of individuals, while crowding refers to the psychological perception of insufficient available space [2], [26]. It is important to differentiate between density and crowding in order to understand the complex interplay between physical and psychological factors in crowded environments [27]. By examining the effects of both density and crowding on individuals, this research aims to provide valuable insights into the implications of crowded surroundings and their impact on social behavior and psychological states.

Crowd Monitoring Techniques

Crowd monitoring is a step before crowd control. Crowd monitoring is responsible for gathering the information needed to generate the contextual knowledge required for crowd control. This crowd management system feature should keep an eye on the region of emphasis and crucial crowd factors (e.g., crowd density, mobility, motion direction, turbulence, accessories, and accidents). The variables seen will be fully determined by the implementation. Traditionally, crowd monitoring has been performed using closed-circuit television (CCTV) schemes or video cameras [28]. However, this technique provides no extra meaningful information beyond the crowd density distribution [29]. Aside from that, the deployment of video cameras demands certain conditions such as appropriate lighting and clear weather, which are not always available during many evening events [29], [30], also, crowd observation may create privacy concerns for people. Another technique has been to investigate users' smart phones to determine their location and, as a result, crowd density. In this technique, users who agree to reveal their locations are continually watched using GPS data analytics.

There is an established practice of deploying extensive closed-circuit camera observation of crowds for safety for existing facilities [31],[32], [33]. This is used in a variety of contexts. For example, television monitors are constantly examined to search for problems. These might be issues caused by numerous types of congestion or problems caused by isolated incidences unrelated to crowds, such as a theft, a fire, or a terrorist planting a bomb. Of course, cameras put mainly in reaction to the latter class of issues (e.g., for what may be generally referred to as 'security') are then accessible for use in response to the earlier class of problems (e.g., for what may be collectively referred to as 'crowd safety'). When crowd density (congestion) surpasses a specific threshold (determined by the crowd's collective goal and the surroundings), danger can develop for a variety of causes. Physical pressure may cause persons to be injured or sections of the physical environment to collapse (for example the collapse of barriers).

Alternatively, the mood of the crowd may change for the worse if they are frustrated in achieving their goal, whether that goal is to get into a football stadium, fight with opposing team supporters, or get home at the end of the working day when an emergency has shut down the commuter transport system throughout a large metropolitan region. It is common practice in crowd management to regulate the arrival rate, stopping it totally when the crowd inside a certain location becomes too large for safety. This applies to admission into an auditorium or a football stadium when it is at capacity, as well as access into a railway or subway station if there is a continuous flow owing to people leaving on outgoing trains, and where entry does not need to be permanently stopped. In the latter instance, input flow may be occasionally halted while the internal throng is decreased by departures, or it may be delayed temporarily by limiting the number or breadth of entry-doors [32].

A smart crowd monitoring system can determine not only the crowd density distribution, but also the direction in which the crowd is travelling by analyzing this data [24]. Furthermore, this spatiotemporal data may be used to improve user mobility prediction. Not all users are interested in sharing data, as is the case with any collaborative sensing system. As a result, modelling and developing novel techniques for predicting crowd density and attributes from a small sample of gathered data are crucial [34]. By the 1970s, the study had progressed to incorporate quantitative approaches that measured the success of crowd control plans and procedures by experimenting with different types of roads and buildings (causing mobility limitations) [35],[36],[37]. During that time, video recording was frequently used to measure crowd movement and management. Researchers and practitioners in the 1990s used improved technology to model pedestrian movements when navigating routes [38].

Crowd Measurement Models

Crowd management is a complicated process that includes features such as crowd modelling for event and infrastructure design, crowd data collecting during crowd monitoring, data analysis for decision making, supplying, and implementing crowd control measures, and so on. Crowd management necessitates the collaboration of numerous engineering and science disciplines, such as physics, computer science, civil engineering, psychology, management, urban design and so on [39],[40]. Crowd modelling, which is focused on simulating crowd situations under various conditions, can aid in the development of better crowd control and management tactics. The traditional modelling approaches can be thought of in terms of microscopic, macroscopic, or mesoscopic scales [41].

Plans for congested pedestrian locations such as city centers, tourist attractions, university campuses, stadium zones, and places of worship need enough capacity for all planned paths as well as effective crowd control techniques. These requirements necessitate an accurate depiction of the temporal spatial distribution of pedestrians and the accompanying service levels in the region. Furthermore, pedestrian responses to design modifications, operating conditions (i.e., incidents), and suggested crowd control techniques must be predictable [42]. Despite significant research into simulating pedestrian movements in congested areas, most models have concentrated on the microscopic behavior of walkers along existing pathways. As a result, the models have significant processing needs, preventing their real-world applicability to large-scale facilities or systems with high demand levels.

Most models fall short of accurately modelling the dynamics of pedestrian route choice, which is critical in very busy areas with several routing possibilities [43]. As a result, pedestrian modelling techniques that can describe the worldwide temporal spatial distribution of pedestrians while being computationally efficient for large-scale applications are required. Such tools are planned to offer architects and planners a suitable foundation for building pedestrian amenities and establishing successful management strategies [44]. Since the 1970s, models of pedestrian mobility have been created. Similar models have been created to explain and forecast macro, meso, and micro movement patterns. Recent breakthroughs in modelling approaches, particularly advances in agent-based simulation, open the door to create integrative and sophisticated models that employ current models as "building bricks." Pedestrian activity may be thought of as the result of two independent factors which are the structure of the street network or urban area, and the placement of specific attractions and amenities on that network. To investigate the impact of each of these, it is required to first monitor and record pedestrian circulation in city streets.

Physical counts or time-lapse photography work have traditionally been used to measure pedestrian movement in the street network[9]. Physical counts lead to counting the number of persons who pass through defined locations, or gates, during a specific time to provide an early indication of flow across the network. Time-lapse photography advances this by capturing the movement of all pedestrians in a certain region and generating 'trail' diagrams to depict their real movement. Fruin in 1971 developed the levels of service (LOS) indicator as an early attempt to expand these methodologies. LOS seeks to quantify pedestrian comfort in urban environments. It measures the flow of pedestrians per unit width of walkway to quantify congestion. There are six service levels specified, ranging To F (severe congestion, more than 82 people per minute per meter of pavement), where progress would be accomplished by shuffling [44].

The (LOS) model allows for the tracking of pedestrian movements in time and location, as well as the identification of crowded areas with potential flow breakdown [45], [46]. The list of the most offers a decision-making environment for evaluating design possibilities, considering effective routes between each origin and destination pair in the region is updated on a regular basis to reflect the area's congestion patterns.

III. DENSITY AND CROWD GENERATION

There is a considerable lack of clarity regarding the definitions of density and crowding. Many researchers have used these terms interchangeably, without differentiating between the physical aspect of density, which relates to spatial constraints, and the psychological aspect of crowding, which pertains to how individuals perceive the constraining features of confined spaces [47], [48], [49],[50], [51]. As a result of this misconception, there is currently a general tendency to define crowding primarily in spatial terms, with little respect for the social and personal elements that may interact with spatial qualities to influence the sensory experience of crowding as shown in figure 3 people generally feel crowded at 4-5 individuals per m²; however, this number fluctuates depending on cultural background and crowd behavior.

Figure **Error! No text of specified style in document.** Indicates Minimum Crowd Density of 1 Person Per Meter Square in LOS Measure, Source: (Fourati et al., 2017)

According to [6], the flow rate of people is the number of people passing through a particular area per unit time. To analyze the flow of people, [52] has developed a level of service standard. He defines six levels of pedestrian flow rates, ranging from level A to level F, with the corresponding density, space, flow rate, and speed values, as listed in Table 3.3

Table 1 Shows Fruin Flow Rate

Fruin Level of Service						
Level of Service	A	B	C	D	E	F
Walkways	>3.25	3.25 to 2.32	2.32 to 1.39	1.39 to 0.93	0.93 to 0.46	<0.46

C = Some Restrictions to Speed	F = Shuffling movements for all
--------------------------------	---------------------------------

Based on the flow rates observed, the state of pedestrian flow can be categorized into six scenarios which are free flow (A and B) where pedestrians move comfortably at a normal speed, light crowd (C) where pedestrians experience a slightly slower pace, constant flow (D) where pedestrians face some restrictions but the crowd is not overly dense, crowded flow (E) where pedestrians move very slowly due to limited space, and heavy crowded or stampede state (F) where the crowd is extremely dense and pedestrians may struggle to maintain balance, potentially leading to falls and injuries [11],[53]. When a large number of people gather closely together, especially when they start encroaching on others' personal space, it raises concerns about overpopulation. This situation becomes problematic and calls for measures to address and mitigate the issue.

Crowd Management Principles and Strategies

Crowd management is crucial not just for handling crowded events, but it is also vital for developing public infrastructure where a high crowd density is predicted [6],[8]. Crowd management is primarily concerned with sustaining crowds and ensuring their comfort; its arrangements cover all aspects, from gathering people into the destination to integrating them into the event to extracting them from the location; it entails more than simply following a formula and planning, given that several changes and unforeseen issues may occur throughout the event [47], [54]. In the context of crowd management, it is important to distinguish it from other strategies such as crowd control and uprising control, as they have different objectives and approaches.

Crowd management primarily focuses on measures aimed at facilitating the movement and satisfaction of individuals within a designated area. This includes implementing strategies to prevent people from dispersing or getting lost within the crowd [55], [56]. On the other hand, crowd control encompasses all efforts undertaken when a large crowd starts to show signs of disorder or has already become unruly [17],[14]. It involves reactive measures aimed at regaining control and restoring order. Another important distinction is the temporal aspect is that crowd management is proactive, focusing on pre-event preparations and preventive measures, while crowd control is reactive, responding to the immediate situation and managing the crowd once it becomes problematic. Management techniques may be classified into three types based on their impact on pedestrians as shown in figure 4.

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.. Unveils the Crowd Event timeline
Source: [54]

This category leads in "Before Event" methods, such as planning and design, "During Event" provisions, which are applied in the event of unforeseen events, and "After Event" policies, which are adopted to reduce the stress of overcrowding following the completion of events [39]. As a result, the most challenging components of crowd control are real-time inspection and presumption.

Pedestrian Crowd Management Strategies (PCMS)

Pedestrian Crowd Management Strategies (PCMS) has also gained tremendous of scholarly contributions.

Table 2 The pedestrian management strategies and the time at which they may be implemented list [55];[56]

Measure	Before event	During event	After event
The removal of physical obstacles	●		
The separation of inflow and outflow of pedestrian traffic	●	●	
Creating one-directional flow	●		
Pressure relief and evacuation strategies must be prepared for any potentially critical areas	●		●
Evacuation measures must be started before an area becomes overcrowded		●	
Intersecting flows should be avoided, and different flow directions should be separated (as dense counter-flows are unstable and dangerous)	●		
A ‘circular’ flow organization, preferably with alternative routes, should be considered	●		

space for emergency vehicles and operations should be reserved

The use of fences (or cordons) to stop large numbers of people needs to be carefully considered, as they may be ineffective or deteriorate the situation

keep people moving (e.g., by rerouting people) rather than stopping them.

Proper signposting must give visitors orientation everywhere about locations of facilities, ways in and out, and emergency exits

Establishing situational awareness and well-functioning communication are crucial

Quick information feedback about the situation in any relevant place and about any relevant factor must be ensured

It is important to have an efficient information flow between the different people and institutions involved (organizers, police, emergency forces, crowd)

The corresponding contingency plan should be applied, and the situation should be continuously (re-)assessed to check for the plausibility of the situational analysis, considering possible alternatives.

give police and emergency forces more autonomous (local) decision-making power and responsibility, particularly when communication is interrupted, or quick action is needed.

Communication must work (both, from a technical and an organizational perspective) It is key to detect, avoid, and respond to critical situations.

Communication is also crucial for the capacity to reduce undesirable interaction effects and to stop dangerous cascading effects

Safety culture must be actively promoted

Managing the build-up and break-up phases of the event, such as the few hours preceding and following the event

guiding the crowd as early as possible provides managers with a wider time window to predict future developments and allows for proactive actions.

Triggering rapid group movement and the occurrence of critical crowd densities should be avoided.

Source: [55]; [56]

Management strategies are not only time-bound, but also method-bound. Crowd management begins as far away from the gathering area as possible, leading the crowd in a comfortable and safe manner. Depending on the size, nature, location, and people engaged, crowd management can begin at public transit hubs, neighboring districts, or even extra-regional sites [57], [4]. Modern stadiums and metropolitan centers, for example, may have walkways that begin at designated highway departure spots. infrastructure such as barriers, ticket machines, and signboards are usually used to help in the development of these paths. This phase is substantially impacted by the disposition of the event. A long-running event without a set core element, such as a pilgrimage, a multi-day festival, or a national celebration, will include a more distributed and free flow of people over its course, as opposed to a football game or a live concert [4]. Numerous such intervention areas have limitations on their validity that must be acknowledged. Table 3 summarizes the multiple conditions for successfully applying crowd control approaches, as well as the limits that inhibit such attempts.

Table **Error! No text of specified style in document.** The different requirements needed to implement effective crowd management and the limitations that inhibit such measures

Requirement	Limitations
Increased situation awareness and decision-making support	confined, biased, and misleading hypothetical situations incapacity to produce unexpected circumstances computer simulations that are not tested and are dubious

	<p>erroneous forecasting of crowd upcoming states</p> <p>inadequate perspective of the crowd (density, movement, flows)</p> <p>restricted assistance to decision-support systems</p>
<p>Reliable real-time monitoring and communication</p>	<p>human-dependent and with minimal observation (e.g., on-the field stewards)</p> <p>Security cameras are not omnipresent, and the majority of data collection is done manually and not in real - time basis data that is coarse-grained and imprecise, with high density</p> <p>Spoken contact and a few common channels are used for communication.</p> <p>There is a dearth of data exchange amongst actors.</p>
<p>Enabling intervention without use of force</p>	<p>Few non-pervasive ways of communication with the audience.</p> <p>Unable to offer immediate preventative feedback to the public.</p> <p>Only fixed displays and loudspeakers are provided.</p> <p>Infrastructure such as barricades and gates is passive and subject to minimal supervision [4].</p>

Source: [4]

Furthermore, crowd control strategies may be divided into two types based on their influence on pedestrians. This difference is inspired by a pedestrian's ability to follow or reject a certain measure. This categorization leads in "hard" measures that people must follow and "soft" standards that people can choose to follow or ignore. Each of these primary classes can be further broken into a plethora of subtypes. Techniques for dealing with tough circumstances "Difficult" techniques need pedestrians to follow them. In this context, the cases in which a single person may "break the rules." Is dismissed. The key approaches that might be explored are listed below in no order. Entry gates are now available in some locations for restricting pedestrian movement via gates [58]. Nonetheless, gate control (deciding when and how long to open) has rarely been regarded as a covariate for improving or optimizing passenger dynamics. Flows are separated by physical things that can be used to avoid crossflows. Only two examples come to mind which are the structural column arrays and public notice boards. Techniques of soft management unlike the previous control action possibilities, "soft" management strategies place a priority on an individual's adherence to a certain piece of information or norm. Because of the considerable complexity added by conformity, the system requires an initial presupposition of total compliance to function. This implies that pedestrians must constantly adhere to relevant regulations and information.

Dynamic floor markings can aid in traffic direction and flow separation. These might be in the shape of arrows or lines. By notifying pedestrians of expected congestion and consequently longer journey times, they may consider deviating to make brief shopping visits to neighboring shops and service kiosks. Ticket machines, vending machines, and kiosks may attract pedestrians to take a shortcut to their destination. Consequently, by strategically distributing these elements across the infrastructure, pedestrian behavior may be governed. To effectively manage the crowd during the Arafat-Muzdalifa pathway on Nafra Day, several crowd management principles should be considered. First and foremost, a comprehensive crowd management plan should be developed, encompassing crowd flow analysis, risk assessment, resource allocation, and emergency response strategies specific to the pathway ([59]Regazzoni et al., 1993; [60] Saeed et al., 2016). Clear and well-marked routes should be designated, accompanied by appropriate signage to guide participants along the pathway and provide crucial information.

Continuous monitoring of the crowd's size, density, and behavior is essential, employing trained personnel and surveillance technologies [32]; [29]. Measures to manage crowd flow and prevent congestion should be implemented, including clearly marked entry and exit points, designated walking areas, and barriers. Effective communication channels should be established to provide real-time instructions and information to the crowd, using loudspeakers, signage, and trained personnel [5];[29]; [61]. Safety and security measures, such as crowd control barriers, medical aid stations, access control, and trained security personnel, should be in place to safeguard participants [31];[60]. Contingency plans and procedures for emergencies should be developed, ensuring the availability of designated emergency assembly points and medical personnel.

Public Participation and Awareness on Pathways Regulations

Public awareness campaigns should be conducted to educate participants about the pathway, safety guidelines, and behavioral expectations. Cultural sensitivity should be exercised, respecting religious practices and customs [15], [61]. Collaboration and coordination among all stakeholders, including event organizers, religious authorities, local authorities, and security personnel, should be fostered through clear communication and a unified command structure[5]. It is crucial to adapt these principles to the specific requirements and guidelines set by the event organizers, religious authorities, and local regulations governing the Arafat-Muzdalifa pathway during Nafra Day. Moreover, crowd management for religious events entails additional considerations due to the unique nature and religious significance of the gathering. Figure 5 shows selected Crowd Management principles and strategies for Arafat Muzdalifah pathway.

Figure 5 indicates Crowd Management Principles

Source: Authors field, 2024

IV. URBAN DESIGN FOR PEDESTRIAN MOVEMENT

Urban design plays a critical role in shaping the movement of pedestrians within urban environments [62],[63]. Creating efficient and pedestrian-friendly systems is essential for promoting sustainable transportation, enhancing urban livability, and fostering vibrant communities [64], [65]. As shown in figure 6, the overview of urban design principles highlights the importance of mixed-use development, walkability, and connectivity. Integrating residential, commercial, and recreational spaces within close proximity reduces the need for long-distance travel and encourages pedestrians to utilize the urban fabric as their primary mode of transportation [62]. Creating well-connected networks of pedestrian pathways and sidewalks enhances accessibility and ensures seamless movement throughout the cityscape. Additionally, designing inviting and aesthetically pleasing public spaces contributes to the overall pedestrian experience and encourages greater foot traffic. Figure 6 illustrates the innovative street in urban design.

Figure 6 Shows the Innovative Street in Urban Design.

Source: [63]

Understanding the factors influencing pedestrian movement is crucial for effective urban design strategies. Population densities, as well as the built environment, play significant roles in shaping pedestrian flow [66], [67]. Areas with higher densities and a diverse range of

activities attract more pedestrians, necessitating efficient movement systems. The layout and design of streets, buildings, and public spaces influence pedestrian behavior, emphasizing the importance of factors such as sidewalk width, street furniture, and the provision of amenities [68]. To ensure efficient pedestrian flow, urban designers employ various strategies in their planning and design processes. These strategies include creating well-defined pedestrian pathways that separate pedestrians from vehicular traffic, providing ample sidewalk space, enhancing pedestrian amenities, creating visually appealing environments, integrating lighting and surveillance measures, and implementing effective wayfinding systems [69], [70], [68]. With a good crowd management strategy, however, this will arranging concrete or plastic barriers to keep pedestrians and vehicles separate, directing people away from places that are prone to jams such as stairs, narrowing corridors, gates, or turnstiles [14], [71]. This is crucial to consider since, depending on the location and the capacity of the region, events are usually overcrowded. By considering these design strategies, cities can promote safe, accessible, and enjoyable pedestrian experiences while facilitating efficient movement within the urban fabric.

Urban Design Principles and Strategies

Urban design principles play a crucial role in shaping the movement of pedestrians within urban environments. These principles encompass various aspects, including land use, transportation planning, and architectural design, all aimed at creating a pedestrian-friendly cityscape [63], [66]. One key principle is the concept of mixed-use development, which encourages the integration of residential, commercial, and recreational spaces within close proximity. This approach reduces the need for long-distance travel and facilitates pedestrian movement by providing destinations within walking distance [62]. Additionally, the principles of walkability and connectivity emphasize the creation of well-connected networks of pedestrian pathways and sidewalks, enabling efficient and safe movement throughout the urban fabric [72]. Designing public spaces that are inviting, accessible, and aesthetically pleasing further enhances the pedestrian experience and encourages greater foot traffic with an excessive experience.

Various factors influence pedestrian movement within urban areas, and understanding these factors is vital for effective urban design strategies. As shown in figure 3.8, firstly, the density and mix of land uses significantly impact pedestrian flow [63],[67]. Areas with high population, along with a diverse range of activities, tend to attract more pedestrians, necessitating efficient movement systems. Secondly, the built environment, including the layout and design of streets, buildings, and public spaces, influences pedestrian movement patterns [73], [74]. Factors such as the width of sidewalks, the presence of street furniture, and the provision of shade and shelter all play a role in shaping pedestrian behavior. Additionally, considerations such as the presence of amenities like benches, lighting, and public art contribute to the overall attractiveness and comfort of pedestrian environments [72], [67]. Lastly, transportation infrastructure and accessibility, including the availability and quality of public transit, parking facilities, and bicycle lanes, also impact pedestrian movement by providing alternative modes of travel and facilitating multi-modal connections.

Figure Error! No style in document. Depicts Factors Influencing Pedestrian Movement in Urban Areas text of specified

As shown in figure 3.8, to ensure efficient pedestrian flow, urban designers employ various strategies in their planning and design processes. One key approach is the creation of well-defined and clearly marked pedestrian pathways that separate pedestrians from vehicular traffic, prioritizing safety and ease of movement [75]. This can be achieved through the design of dedicated pedestrian-only zones, such as pedestrian malls or plazas, or by implementing traffic calming measures and reducing vehicle speeds in shared spaces. Another strategy involves the provision of ample sidewalk space, considering factors like width, continuity, and accessibility [67]. Wider sidewalks accommodate higher volumes of pedestrians, while continuous and barrier-free pathways allow for unobstructed movement. Enhancing pedestrian amenities, such as seating areas, public restrooms, and drinking fountains, further encourages pedestrians to linger and navigate the urban environment comfortably.

Furthermore, designers focus on creating visually appealing and engaging pedestrian environments through thoughtful landscaping, urban greening, and public art installations [76],[72]. These elements contribute to the overall ambiance, making walking more enjoyable and encouraging pedestrian interaction with the surroundings. Designing pedestrian-oriented plazas, squares, and parks as focal points within the urban fabric also serves as gathering spaces and promotes social cohesion. Integrating lighting systems and surveillance measures enhance safety and security during nighttime hours, encouraging pedestrian activity throughout the day. Lastly, effective wayfinding systems, including clear signage and intuitive navigation aids, assist pedestrians in understanding their surroundings, reducing confusion, and facilitating efficient movement from one destination to another [10].

In conclusion, urban design strategies for pedestrian movement systems revolve around creating pedestrian-friendly environments that prioritize safety, accessibility, and efficiency. By considering urban design principles, understanding the factors influencing pedestrian movement, and employing design strategies focused on efficient flow, cities can enhance the walking experience, promote sustainable transportation, and foster vibrant and inclusive urban spaces. Figure 7 shows the selected urban planning strategies for Arafat Muzdalifah pathway.

Figure 8 Illustrates Selected Urban Planning Strategies for Arafat Muzdalifah Pathway

V. CONCLUSION

For further effective crowd management during Hajj pilgrimage in Saudi Arabia, the study depicts that, it is essential to focus on urban design strategies for pedestrian movement systems are essential for creating sustainable, pedestrian-friendly cities. By incorporating the principles of mixed-use development, walkability, and connectivity, and considering factors such as density, the built environment, and transportation infrastructure, urban designers can develop efficient and inviting pedestrian environments. By implementing design strategies that prioritize safety, accessibility, and aesthetic appeal, cities can promote active transportation, enhance urban livability, and foster vibrant and inclusive communities. The model generates a variety of performance measurements and includes animation features to aid in comparing the efficacy of design options and control strategies [77].

REFERENCES

- [1] M.Alkhadim, K. Gidado, & N.Painting, "Risk management: the effect of FIST on perceived safety in crowded large space buildings." *Safety Science*. Vol. 108, pp 29 – 38. 2018.
- [2] F. Aros-Vera, A. Sadeghi, R.Y. Sinaki, & D. Sormaz, A simulation-based framework for checkpoint design in large-scale crowd management: Case study of the papal mass in Philadelphia. *Safety Science*. Vol.127, pp (10470),1. 2020.
- [3] F.T. Illiyas, S.K. MMani, A. Pradeepkumar, & K. Mohan, Human stampedes during religious festivals: A comparative review of mass gathering emergencies in India. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*. Vol. 5, pp 10-18. 2013.
- [4] C. Martella, J. Li, C. Conrado, & A. Vermeeren, "On current crowd management practices and the need for increased situation awareness, prediction, and intervention." *Safety Science*, Vol. 91, pp 381-393. 2017.
- [5] H. M. Al-Ahmadi, I. Reza, A. Jamal, W.S. Alhalabi, & K.J. Assi, Preparedness for mass gatherings: a simulation-based framework for flow control and management using crowd monitoring data. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*. Vol. 46(5),4985-4997. 2021a.
- [6] J. Fourati, B. Issaoui, & K. Zidi, "Literature Review of Crowd Management: A Hajj Case Study." ICINCO. 2017- Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Informatics in Control, Automation and Robotics. Vol. 1. pp 346-351. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0006472103460351>.
- [7] B. Krausz, & C. Bauckhage, Analyzing pedestrian behavior in crowds for automatic detection of congestions. *2011 IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops (ICCV Workshops)*. IEEE. 2011.
- [8] Y.Turgut, & C. Bozdog, "Modeling pedestrian group behavior in crowd evacuations." *Fire and Materials*, Vol.46. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fam.2978> . 2021
- [9] D. Helbing, L. Buzna, A. Johansson, & T. "Werner, Self-organized pedestrian crowd dynamics: Experiments, simulations, and design solutions." *Transportation Science*. Vol. 39(1),1-24. 2005.
- [10] A. M. Alkharoubi, Wayfinding for pedestrians in the crowded areas of Al-Hajj: How can wayfinding system designs increase the efficiency of wayfinding and navigation performances for pedestrian pilgrims during the Islamic pilgrimage (Al-Hajj). *University of Minnesota*. 2020.
- [11] T.Sakuma, T. Mukai, & S. Kuriyama, "Psychological model for animating crowded pedestrians." *Computer Animation and Virtual Worlds*. Vol.16(3), pp 343-351. 2005.
- [12] S. A. H. Ai-Gadhi, "A Review Study of Crowd Behavior and Movement." In *J. King Saud Univ*. Vol. 8, (1). 1996.

- [13] Y. Yang, J Yu, C. Wang, & J. Wen, Risk Assessment of Crowd-Gathering in Urban Open Public Spaces Supported by Spatio-Temporal Big Data. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*. Vol. 14(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14106175>. 2022.
- [14] R. M. Favaretto, L. Dihl, & S.R. Musse, S. R. "Detecting Crowd Features in Video Sequences." <https://doi.org/10.1109/SIBGRAP.2016.34>. 2016.
- [15] D. Haghghi, M. Quan Ngo, P. Delir Haghghi, & F. Burstein, "A Crowd Monitoring Framework using Emotion Analysis of Social Media for Emergency Management in Mass Gatherings." 2015.
- [16] M.O. Khozium, A.G. Abuarafah, & E. AbdRabou, "A proposed computer-based system architecture for crowd management of pilgrims using thermography." *Life Science Journal*. Vol. 9(2), pp 377 – 383. 2012.
- [17] J. Abbott, & M.W. Geddie, "Event and venue management: Minimizing liability through effective crowd management techniques." *Event Management*, 6(4), 259-270. 2000.
- [18] Y.A. Alaska, A.D. Aldawas, N. A. Aljerian, Z. A. Memish, & S. Suner, "The impact of crowd control measures on the occurrence of stampedes during Mass Gatherings: The Hajj experience." *Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*. Vol. 15, pp 67-70. 2017.
- [19] M. Batty, J. Desyllas, & E. Duxbury, "Safety in numbers? Modelling crowds and designing control for the Notting Hill Carnival." *Urban Studies*, 40(8), 1573-1590. 2003.
- [20] R. Stanton, & G. Wanless, "Pedestrian movement." *Safety Science*. Vol. 18(4), pp 291-300. 1995.
- [21] J. Zhang, S. Cao, D. Salden, & J. Ma, "Homogeneity and activeness of crowd on aged pedestrian dynamics." *Procedia Computer Science*. Vol. 83, pp 361-368. 2016.
- [22] N. Fridman, & G.A. Kaminka, "Modeling pedestrian crowd behavior based on a cognitive model of social comparison theory." *Computational and Mathematical Organization Theory*. Vol 16(4), pp 348-372. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10588-010-9082-2>. 2010.
- [23] B. Kaban, "Crowd dynamics: modelling pedestrian movement and associated generated forces." *Université Paris-Est*. 2016.
- [24] D. Helbing, A. Johansson, & H.Z. Al-Abideen, "Dynamics of Crowd Disasters: An Empirical study." *Physical Review E*. Vol. 75(4), 2007.
- [25] K. M. Ngai, F.M. Burkle, A. Hsu, & E. B. Hsu, "Human Stampedes: a systematic review of historical and peer-reviewed sources." *Disaster Medicine and Public Health Preparedness*. Vol. 3(4), pp 191 – 195. 2009.
- [26] J. Srivastava, & A. Singh, "Effect of Perceived Crowding on the Mental Health of Adolescence. *Indian Journal of Scientific Research*. pp 138-144. 2017.
- [27] W.C. Sullivan, & C-Y. Chang." Mental health and the built environment. In *Making healthy places*. Pp. 106-116). 2011.
- [28] C.S. Regazzoni, A. Tesi, & V. Murino, "A real-time vision system for crowding monitoring". *Proceedings of IECON'th Annual Conference of IEEE Industrial Electronics*. Pp 19-93. 1993.
- [29] J. E. Mallah, F. Carrino, O.A. Khaled, & E. Mugellini, "Crowd monitoring." *International Conference on Distributed, Ambient, and Pervasive Interactions*. 2015.
- [30] M. Wirz, T. Franke, D. Roggen, E. Mitleton-Kelly, P. Lukowicz, & G. Tr"oster, "Probing crowd density through smartphones in city-scale mass gatherings." *EPJ Data Science*. Vol. 2(1), pp 1-24. 2013.
- [31] A. C. Davies, J. H. Yin, & S.A. Velastin, "Crowd Monitoring Using Image Processing." *Electronics & Communication Engineering Journal*. Vol. 7(1), 37-47. 1995
- [32] D. Dickinson, & M.-C. Villeval., "Does Monitoring Decrease Work Effort?: The Complementarity Between Agency and Crowding-out Theories." *Games and Economic Behavior*. Vol. 63(1), pp 56-76. 2008.
- [33] J.C. Moskop, D.P. Sklar, J.M. Geiderman, R. M. Schears, & K.J. Bookman, "Emergency Department Crowding, Part 2- Barriers to Reform and 1 Strategies to Overcome hem." *Annals of Emergency Medicine*. Vol. 53(5), pp 612-617. 2009.
- [34] B. Guo, Z. Yu, X. Zhou, & D. Zhang, "From Participatory Sensing to Mobile Crowd Sensing." *2014 IEEE International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communication Workshops (PERCOM WORKSHOPS)*. IEEE. 2014.
- [35] A. Jabbari, K.L. Almalki, B.-Y. Choi, & S. Song, "ICE-MoCha Intelligent Crowd Engineering Using Mobility Characterization and Analytics. *Sensors*. Vol. 19(5), 2019.
- [36] Y. Minegishi, "Occupant Evacuation Elevators as a Measure for Crowd Management and Evacuation for People with Mobility Impairments in High-rise Buildings." *Japan Architectural Review*. Vol. 4(2), pp 391-402. 2021.
- [37] G. Solmaz, F.-J. Wu, F. Cirillo, E. Kovacs, J.R. Santana, L. Sánchez, P. Sotres, & L. Munoz, "Toward Understanding Crowd Mobility in Smart Cities Through the Internet of Things." *IEEE Communications Magazine*. Vol. 57(4), 40-46. 2019.
- [38] A. Johansson, M. Batty, K. Hayashi, O. Bar, D. Al, Marcozzi, & Z.A. Memish, Crowd and environmental management during mass gatherings. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*. Vol. 12(2), pp 150-156. 2012).
- [39] V.X. Gong, W. Daamen, A. Bozzon, & S.P. Hoogendoorn, "Crowd characterization for crowd management using social media data in city events." *Travel Behaviour and Society*. Vol. 20, pp 192-212. 2020.
- [40] L. M. Kamarudin, N. A. R. A. Aziz, & A. Ramely "Understanding Crowd Management in Sports Events: A Preliminary Study." 2022.
- [41] N. Bellomo, D. Clarke, L. Gibelli, P. Townsend, & B. Vreugdenhil, "Human behaviours in evacuation crowd dynamics: From modelling to "big data" toward crisis management." *Physics of Life Reviews*. Vol. 18, pp 1-21. 2016.

- [42] A. Turner, & A. Penn, "Encoding natural movement as an agent-based system: an investigation into human pedestrian behaviour in the built environment." *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*. Vol. 29(4), pp 473-490, 2002.
- [43] A. Abdelghany, K. Abdelghany, I.S. Mahmassani, & A. Al-Zahrani, "Dynamic simulation assignment model for pedestrian movements in crowded networks." *Transportation Research Record*. Vol. 2316(1), pp 95-105, 2012.
- [44] M. Haklay, D. O'Sullivan, M. Thurstain-Goodwin, & T. Schelhorn, "So go downtown. *Simulating Pedestrian Movement in Town Centres*." *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*. Vol. 28(3), pp 343-359 2001.
- [45] W. E. Hammitt, G.T Kyle, & C.-O. Oh, "Comparison of place bonding models in recreation resource management." *Journal of Leisure Research*. Vol. 41(1), pp 57-72. 2009.
- [46] M. Mashhadawi, "Mass Motion evacuation model validation." LUTVDG/TVBB. 2016.
- [47] A. E. Berlonghi, "Understanding and planning for different spectator crowds." *Safety Science*. Vol. 18(4), pp 239-247. 1995.
- [48] J. Edney, "Theories of Human Crowding: A Review." *Environment and Planning A*. Vol. 9(11), pp 1211-1232. 1977.
- [49] J. Qurashi, M. Korstanje, R. Raj, & K. Griffin, "Hajj: The movement and behavior of crowds" *Risk and Safety Challenges for Religious Tourism and Events*. Vol 52. 2018.
- [50] S. Saegert, "Crowding: Cognitive overload and behavioural constraint." *Environmental Design Research*. Vol 2(3), pp 254-260. 1973.
- [51] D. Stokols, "On the distinction between density and crowding: some implications for future research." *Psychological Review*. Vol. 79 (3), 1972.
- [52] J.J. Fruin, "Pedestrian Planning and Design. Metropolitan Association of Urban Planners and Environmental Planners." 1971
- [53] J.E. Stockdale, "Crowding: Determinants and Effects. In *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*. Vol. 11. Pp 197-247.1978.
- [54] J. Li, H. De Ridder, A. Vermeeren, C. Conrado, C. Martella, & P.D. Candidate, "Designing for Crowd Well-Being: Current Designs, Strategies and Future Design Suggestions." 2013.
- [55] D. Helbing, & P. Mukerji, "Crowd disasters as systemic failures: analysis of the Love Parade disaster." In *EPJ Data*. 2012.
- [56] H. Zhao, T. Thrash, M. Kapadia, K. Wolff, C. Hölscher, D. Helbing, & V.R. Schinazi, "Assessing crowd management strategies for the 2010 Love Parade disaster using computer simulations and virtual reality." *Journal of the Royal Society Interface*. Vol. 17(167), pp 20200116. 2020
- [57] F. Li, S. Chen, X. Wang, & F. Feng, "Pedestrian evacuation modelling and simulation on metro platforms considering panic impacts." *Procedia-Social and Behavioural Sciences*. Vol.138, pp 314 – 322. 2014.
- [58] D. Bauer, S. Seer, & N. Brandle, "Macroscopic pedestrian flow simulation for designing crowd control measures in public transport after special events." *Proceedings of the 2007 Summer Computer Simulation Conference*. 2007
- [59] C.S. Regazzoni, A. Tesei, A. & V. Murino, "A real Time Vision System for Crowding Monitoring." *Proceeding of IECON'th Annual Conference of IEEE Industrial Electronics*. Pp 19-93. 1993.
- [60] S. N. Saeed, A. Abid, E.U. Waraich, S. Atta, A. Naseer, A. A. Sheikh, & E. Felemban, "Crowd-A framework for monitoring of identifiable crowd." *2016 12th International Conference on Innovations in Information Technology (IIT)*. IEEE. 2016.
- [61] C.A. Pouw, F. Toschi, F. van Schadewijk, & A. Corbetta, "Monitoring Physical distancing for crowd management: Real-time trajectory and group analysis." *Plos One*. Vol. 15,(10) . 2020).
- [62] A. Forsyth, "What is a walkable place? The walkability debate in urban design." *Urban Design International*, Vol. 20(4), pp 274-292. <https://doi.org/10.1057/udi.2015.22>. 2015.
- [63] J. Rui, & F. Othengrafen, "Examining the Role of Innovative Streets in Enhancing Urban Mobility and Livability for Sustainable Urban Transition: A Review." In *Sustainability* (Switzerland). Vol. 15,(7). 2023 MDPI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15075709>
- [64] N. Fazlina Khashim, M. Ismail, A.S. Hassan, & N. T. Al-Ashwal, "A Study on Kevin Lynch's Urban Design Elements: Precinct 9 East Putrajaya". <http://TuEngr.com>. 2017.
- [65] N.N. Patricios, Urban design principles of the original neighbourhood concepts , Vol. 6, Issue 1. 2002
- [66] S. Salwa, S. Mahdzar, & S. Jaberolansar, "A Review of Effective Factors of Urban Design with an Emphasis on Pedestrian Movement Sustainable Design-Space Syntax Spatial Network & Static Activities Analysis: Sociability vs Accessibility on Urban Street Life View project bus stop planning View project A Review of Effective Factors of Urban Design with an Emphasis on Pedestrian Movement." *J. Basic. Appl. Sci. Res*. Vol. 4(5), pp. 97-104. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332189947>. 2014.
- [67] A. Stanitsa, S. H. Hallett, & S. Jude, Investigating pedestrian behaviour in urban environments: A Wi-Fi tracking and machine learning approach. *Multimodal Transportation*, Vol. 2(1), pp 100049. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.multra.2022.100049>
- [68] S. Van Der Spek, "Optimizing Routing and Safety for Pedestrians. A tool for pedestrian oriented design Geomatics Synthesis Project: Monitoring flows and occupation patterns with Wi-Fi View project Sensing the City View project." <http://urbanism.nl> . 2006.
- [69] K. Al-Kodmany, "Crowd management and urban design: New scientific approaches." *Urban Design International*, Vol. 18(4), pp 282 – 295. 2013.
- [70] S. Albeverio, D. Andrey, P. Giordano, A. Vancheri "The Dynamics of Complex Urban Systems An Interdisciplinary Approach." 2007
- [71] N. Wijermans, C. Conrado, M. van Steen, C. Martella, & J. Li "A landscape of crowd-management support: An integrative approach." *Safety Science*, Vol. 86, pp 142-164. 2016.

- [72] K. Skolan, F. Arkitektur, & O. Samhällsbyggnad, "Pedestrian movement and its effect on sociability of public spaces A case study on Amsterdam SHAGHAYEGH TAVAKOLI." 2017.
- [73] A. Sohail, M. A. Cheema, M. E. Ali, A. N. Toosi, & H.A. Rakha, "Data-Driven Approaches for Road Safety: A Comprehensive Systematic Literature Review." 2022.
- [74] A. Wang, A. Biswas, H. Admoni, & A. Steinfeld, "Towards Rich, Portable, and Large-Scale Pedestrian Data Collection". <http://arxiv.org/abs/2203.01974>. 2022.
- [75] M. Bezbradica, H.J. & Ruskin, "Understanding Urban Mobility and Pedestrian Movement." 2019.
- [76] National Association of City Transportation Officials "Special Pedestrian Districts and Site Design for Pedestrian." 2014
- [77] J. Fourati, B. Issaoui, & K. Zidi, "Literature review of crowd management: A Hajj case study." *ICINCO 2017-Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Informatics in Control, Automation and Robotics*, Vol.1, pp 346-351. 2017. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0006472103460351>